

CHET TILI O‘QITISHIDA OLAMNING LISONIY VA KONSEPTUAL MANZARASINI INTEGRATSIYA QILISH: RUS VA O‘ZBEK TILLARINING TAQQOSLAMA TAHLILI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqola xorijiy til o‘qitilishi va o‘rganilayotgan til mamlakatining madaniyati o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro bog‘liqlikni o‘rganishga bag‘ishlangan. Tilda mavjud bo‘lgan tarixiy, madaniy va siyosiy kontekstlarni chuqurroq anglash uchun til egalarining dunyoqarash konsepsiyalarini o‘quv jarayoniga integratsiya qilish muhimligi ko‘rib chiqilgan. Muallif til manzarasi – bu borliq haqidagi bilimlar tizimi ekanligini ta’kidlaydi va u tildan foydalanuvchilarning dunyoni qabul qilishiga xos jihatlarni aks ettirib, kognitiv jarayonlarga jiddiy ta’sir ko‘rsatishini qayd etadi. Rus va o‘zbek tillaridagi til va konseptual dunyo manzarasidagi farqlar tarixiy-madaniy va etnolingvistik omillarga asoslangan misollar orqali yoritilgan. Ushbu farqlarning bilishlari madaniyatlararo muloqotni yanada samarali qilish, tarjima va xorijiy til o‘qitish jarayonini takomillashtirishga xizmat qilishi alohida ta’kidlanadi.

KALIT SO‘ZLAR

til manzarasi, konseptual dunyo manzarasi, madaniyatlararo muloqot, xorijiy til o‘qitilishi, dunyoqarash konsepsiyalari, kognitiv lingvistika, rus tili, o‘zbek tili, madaniy an’analar, til xususiyatlari.

ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ЯЗЫКОВОЙ И КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНОЙ КАРТИНЫ МИРА В ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА: СОПОСТАВИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ РУССКОГО И УЗБЕКСКОГО ЯЗЫКОВ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена изучению взаимосвязи между преподаванием иностранного языка и культурой страны изучаемого языка. Рассматривается важность интеграции мировоззренческих концепций носителей языка в учебный процесс для глубокого понимания исторических, культурных и политических контекстов, содержащихся в языковых единицах. Автор подчеркивает, что языковая картина мира, как система знаний о действительности, отражает специфику мировосприятия носителей языка и оказывает существенное влияние на когнитивные процессы. Приведены

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

языковая картина мира, концептуальная картина мира, межкультурная коммуникация, преподавание иностранного языка, мировоззренческие концепции, когнитивная

примеры различий в языковой и концептуальной картинах мира в русском и узбекском языках, основанные на историко-культурных и этнолингвистических факторах. Подчеркивается, что знание этих различий способствует более эффективной межкультурной коммуникации, а также совершенствованию процесса перевода и преподавания иностранного языка.

лингвистика, русский язык, узбекский язык, культурные традиции, языковые особенности.

INTEGRATION OF LINGUISTIC AND CONCEPTUAL WORLDVIEWS INTO FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the study of the relationship between foreign language teaching and the culture of the country of the target language. The importance of integrating worldview concepts of native speakers into the teaching process for a deep understanding of historical, cultural and political contexts contained in linguistic units is considered. The author emphasizes that the linguistic picture of the world, as a system of knowledge about reality, reflects the specificity of the world perception of native speakers and has a significant impact on cognitive processes. Examples of differences in linguistic and conceptual pictures of the world in Russian and Uzbek languages based on historical-cultural and ethno-linguistic factors are given. It is emphasized that knowledge of these differences contributes to more effective intercultural communication, as well as improving the process of translation and foreign language teaching.

KEYWORDS

linguistic picture of the world, conceptual picture of the world, intercultural communication, foreign language teaching, worldview concepts, cognitive linguistics, Russian language, Uzbek language, cultural traditions, linguistic features.

Nowadays, the relationship between teaching a foreign language and the culture of the country of the target language seems obvious, since the language functions as a full-fledged means of professional intercultural communication. The main task of foreign language teachers is the maximum development of communicative competences of students. To achieve this goal, a foreign language should be studied in inseparable connection with cultural and worldview features of native speakers.

The study and integration into language practice of worldview concepts of native speakers contributes to the understanding of historical, political and cultural connotations of linguistic units. The linguistic picture of the world is understood as a set of knowledge and perceptions of the subject about real or mental reality, expressed in linguistic categories. Researchers admit that the linguistic

picture of the world precedes the specialised scientific pictures of the world (physical, chemical, etc.), as language records historical, national and universal experience that determines the ways of perception and interpretation of reality.

According to Y. D. Apresyan, each natural language reflects a specific way of conceptualising the world, forming a system of views imposed on its speakers [1, C.357]. The way of conceptualisation of reality is partly universal, but at the same time it has national specificity, which causes differences in the perception of the world by representatives of different language communities. This aspect was studied in the works of W. Humboldt, F. Boas, E. Sapir and B. Warf. Warf, who, while recognising the common biological and cognitive bases of thinking,

emphasised the differences between linguistic pictures of the world.

Modern studies of the linguistic picture of the world take into account aspects of folk taxonomy, including nominations of body parts, related terms, names of flora and fauna, and colour denotations (B. Berlin, P. Kay, A. Vejbicka). According to the culturological hypothesis, the detail of the classification reflects the significance of the relevant aspects for a particular culture. At the end of the 20th century in linguistics and philosophy, many works devoted to the linguistic picture of the world emerged (G. A. Brutyan, S. A. Vasiliev, Y. N. Karaulov, G. V. Kolshansky, E. S. Kubryakova, etc.), which led to the realisation of the need to further study the issues of the correlation between collective and individual consciousness, types of thinking, as well as logical problems of language. These studies are of particular importance in the context of improving the effectiveness of foreign language teaching.

The connection between the linguistic and conceptual picture of the world becomes the subject of close attention of modern linguists and cognitive scientists. The conceptual picture of the world includes not only linguistic categories, but also broader cognitive structures that determine the ways of comprehending and interpreting reality. Within the framework of cognitive linguistics the mechanisms of concept formation, their structuring in the consciousness of native speakers, as well as the influence of language on the processes of categorisation and awareness of the surrounding world are studied.

Studies in this field show that differences in conceptual world pictures between language communities are conditioned by cultural traditions, historical development and social norms. The influence of the linguistic picture of the world on cognitive processes is manifested in the specifics of metaphorisation, symbolism and conceptual categorisation, which is confirmed by the works of J. Lakoff, M. Johnson, A. Vezhbitskaya and other scientists. Thus, the study of linguistic and conceptual picture of the world is an important aspect of modern linguistics and intercultural communication, contributing to a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of interaction between language, thinking and culture.

Within the framework of the linguistic picture of the world, the connection between language and thinking, the surrounding world, cultural and ethnic phenomena, as well as phenomena within language itself is realised. «Language is a system of understanding, that is, ultimately, world understanding; language is world understanding itself», - wrote A.F. Losev [2, p. 822].

The linguistic picture of the world is a system of knowledge about reality embodied in linguistic units. It is formed through the lexicon, grammatical structures and idiomatic expressions peculiar to a particular language. The Russian and Uzbek languages have different ways of perceiving the surrounding world, which is connected with historical-cultural and ethno-linguistic factors.

In Russian, the linguistic picture of the world is closely intertwined with the European tradition of perception of reality and the influence of Orthodox culture. Concepts such as «судьба» – «fate», «душа» - «soul», «вера»- «faith» have deep philosophical and religious roots. In the Uzbek language, the linguistic picture of the world reflects the peculiarities of the rural way of life, which is manifested in the vocabulary associated with farming, herding and traditional social institutions (e.g. «zor» - rural field, «xalq» - people, «duo» - prayer, «mehnat» - labour).

The conceptual picture of the world includes not only linguistic features, but also cognitive mechanisms of perception of reality. It reflects the system of values, mental attitudes and cultural traditions of native speakers.

The authors of the collective monograph «The Role of the Human Factor in Language: Language and the World Picture», based on the recognition of the breadth of thinking in relation to language, postulate that the linguistic world picture is a part of the conceptual world picture. The authors consider the most adequate understanding of the conceptual picture of the world to be «its definition as an initial global image of the world, underlying the human worldview, representing the essential properties of the world in the understanding of its carriers and being the result of all human spiritual activity» [3, p.21]. [3, c.21].

In the Russian language, the conceptual picture of the world is formed on the basis of a wide range of borrowed concepts, the influence of various philosophical schools and the historical experience of multicultural interaction. In the Uzbek language, the conceptual picture of the world is based on the traditions of rural lifestyle, communalism and religious ideas about spirituality. For example, Uzbek culture attaches special importance to the concept of «mehr-shafqat» (kindness and mercy), which is reflected in language constructions and communication etiquette.

The linguistic and conceptual pictures of the world in Russian and Uzbek languages show the differences in cultural traditions, historical path and ways of perceiving the surrounding world. The study of these pictures helps to deepen the understanding of language and gives a deeper insight into the mentality of different peoples.

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